

ISSUES FOR IMPROVEMENT THE CONCEPT OF CREATING BRAND VALUE OF FOOD PRODUCTS

Khodjiev Ibrohim Ikramovich

Independent researcher, Tashkent State University of Economics

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As is known, in creating and managing brand value, product promotion, additional values, and psychological relationships between the consumer and the manufacturer are of decisive importance. In particular, brand positioning, shaping its position in the minds of consumers, and maintaining it in conditions of constant competition have become one of the important research areas in the fields of marketing and management today.

The brand in marketing and its theoretical foundations were developed and improved by Professor David Aaker of the University of California[2]. Aaker and Joachimstha's research identified 4 main determinants of brand value, including: consumer awareness of the brand, perceived value, brand associations, and loyalty. S. Davis's research[3] on the formation of brands by enterprises, effective communication with consumers about the brand, and increasing its attractiveness are noteworthy.

Keller created the Customer-Based Brand Equity model, which considers the brand as a means of creating added value for the enterprise and its basis to be the consumer.[4] This model is based on the view that "the strength of a brand depends on the changes in the perceptions, feelings, and experiences of customers about the brand over time."

J. N. Kapferer's research on the creation, development, and maintenance of brand value[5] focused on the creation of brands, the management of product trademarks, the role of innovations in the development and renewal of brands, and trends in corporate branding and modern brand management.

A. N. Andreev's research shows that the basis of creating brand value is associated with working with specific approaches to consumer segments.[6]

Foreign scholars R. Dissanayake proposed models for coordinating advertising and budgets of dairy companies by brand. The study proposes a methodology for determining brand values, brand advantages and strategy creation budgets.[7]

Using the Customer-Based Brand Equity model, the consumer value of dairy brands for the country of Nepal was determined by S. Kumar [8].

M. Dubinina, a scientist from the Commonwealth of Independent States, was the first to conduct a study on the creation of dairy brand value.[9] The study presents a set of characteristics and features that determine the strategic

planning process for a dairy brand with the potential to create integrated value, the stage of selecting indicators of consumer brand and brand value, and the most important value determinants.

N. A. Karpenko identified the factors that increase the competitiveness of Belarusian dairy brands based on the identification of specific aspects of value creation.[10]

Scientists of our republic have conducted a number of studies aimed at conducting marketing research in the food market, developing strategic marketing and market activities of enterprises. In particular, Zh. Imomov conducted a study aimed at satisfying the population's need for agricultural products based on the effective use of quality management at food manufacturing enterprises[11].

M. Aminova substantiated the theoretical aspects of the concepts of the product sales system in the B2B food market and the need and importance of developing this market.[12] Hakimov H., Hamdamov Sh. outlined the modern stages of development of the food industry and the reforms being carried out in the sector, as well as their main development trends.

S.Eshmatov's research conducted a strategic analysis aimed at developing Uzbekistan's food exports and identified the main directions for developing marketing strategies. [13]

O. Kasimov's research analyzed the position of Uzbek packaged iced tea brands and their market share, and gave recommendations on the use of marketing methods and theories such as competitive advantage, branding, re-styling, benchmarking, and distribution.[1]

However, the issues of creating brand value in the food market and forming and managing branding strategies in enterprises in the research conducted by Uzbek scientists have not been fully developed. Therefore, there is a need to create additional models that will ensure the measurement and development of consumer and corporate brand value of food brands in the Uzbek market.

References:

1. O. Kasimov, U. Kasimov, Analysis of the Uzbek packaged iced tea market, brands and competition between them. 21.07.2014. <http://www.biznes-daily.uz/uz/birjaexpert/22955-ozbkiston-qadoqlangan-yaxna-choy-bozori-tahlili-brndlar-va-ular-ortasidagi-raqobat>.
2. Aaker, David A. (2004a), Brand Portfolio Strategy. Creating Relevance, Differentiation, Energy, Leverage and Clarity. New York, Free Press. (2004b), "Leveraging the Corporate Brand" California Management Review, 46 (3), 6-18.
3. Davis, Scott M. (2002), Brand Asset Management: Driving Profitable Growth through Your Brands, San Francisco, Josey Bass.
4. Keller, Kevin Lane (1993), "Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity", Journal of Marketing, 57 (January), 1-22.
5. Kapferer Jean-Noel. Brand Forever. Moscow: Vershina, 2007. - 448 p.: ill, table. - ISBN 5-9626-0015-0.
6. Andreeva, A.N. Portfolio approach to luxury brand management in the fashion business: basic concepts, retrospective and possible scenarios. Scientific report / A. N. Andreeva // St. Petersburg: Research Institute of Management, St. Petersburg State University, 2006. - No. 27 (R) - 2006. - 29 p
6. D.M.R.Dissanayake. Brand building strategies and customer buying decisions: A study on growing up milk powder market of Sri Lanka. NSBM Business & Management Journal Volume 1 Number 1 January 2015.
7. S.Kumar. Measuring Consumer-Based Brand Equity: A Case Study of Dairy Milk Brands in Nepal. Teaching Assistant (MBS, M.Phil.), Tribhuvan University, Shanker Dev Campus. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323318962>
8. Дубинина М. Формирование ценности бренда молочной продукции региона. Специальность 08.00.05. — экономика и управление народным хозяйством: маркетинг. Автореферат. Диссертации на соискание ученой степени к.э.н. Ростов-на-Дону — 2010.
9. И. А. Фукова, Н. А. Карпенко. Брендинг молочной продукции в республике беларусь. Белорусская и российская модели социально ориентированной экономики. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=35067006>
10. J. Imomov. Increasing the competitiveness of products based on the development of a quality management system. "Business - Expert". 27.11.2017 | Issue: №11(119)-2017. <http://www.biznes-daily.uz/uz/birjaexpert/53027-sifat-menejment-tizimini-rivojlarıstır-asosida-mahsulotlar-raqobatbardoshligini-oshirih>

11. M. Aminova. Improving the sales system in the B2B market of food products. 11.11.2019. <http://www.biznes-daily.uz/uz/birjaexpert/70014-oziq-ovkat-tovarlari-b2b-bozorida-sotish-tizimini-tasimistir>.
12. Hakimov H., Hamdamov Sh. Factors of development of the food industry in Uzbekistan. "Business-Expert" magazine, 2016, issue 4. <http://www.biznes-daily.uz/ru/birjaexpert/39762>
13. Ikramov, M., Eshmatov, S., Samadov, A., Imomova, G., & Boboerova, M. (2021). Management marketing strategy for formation of local brand of milk and dairy products in the digital economy. *Revista geintec-gestao inovacao e tecnologias*, 11(2), 443-466.

